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**EFL Teachers' and Students' Attitudes towards Podcasts as Instructional
Material to Enhance Students' Listening Skills**

A Case Study of Third-Year Licence Students at Relizane University

*Thesis submitted to the Department of English in partial fulfillment of the requirements
for the Degree of Master in Language and Communication*

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Dedication

This work is dedicated to:

My beloved Parents

The reason for what I become today

Your unwavering support and encouragement, both morally and physically, have been a constant throughout my entire academic journey, shaping my path and fueling my determination

To my brothers and their wonderful kids

To my family members

I am really thankful for your encouragement and guidance

OUSSAMA

This thesis is dedicated to my family,

whose unwavering support, encouragement, and confidence in my abilities have been immeasurable throughout this entire process.

Their presence has been a constant source of inspiration and strength, guiding me to remain strong through all the challenges and to keep pushing forward toward my goals.

To them, I dedicate my sincere gratitude.

WALID

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Abstract

Listening is crucially important skill in language learning, it is the receptive skill of understanding spoken language. Podcasts, on the other hand, are online audio publications that can be downloaded and listened to on portable devices like smartphones, laptops, and tablets. Therefore, the researchers attempted to understand the attitudes of EFL teachers and students towards podcasts as an instructional material to enhance students' listening skills. This study aimed to explore the attitudes and perceptions of both EFL teachers and students towards the use of podcasts as instructional material to enhance students' listening skills. To carry out this study, a qualitative approach was selected, employing two distinct questionnaires. One questionnaire was administered to a sample of thirty-nine (39) third-year EFL students at the Department of English Language, University of Relizane, to understand their perceptions, and attitudes towards using podcasts for listening skill development. A separate questionnaire was administered to a sample of ten (10) EFL teachers from the same department to explore their perceptions of the pedagogical value of podcasts, their attitudes towards their use in language instruction, and their insights into the benefits and challenges of podcast integration. The findings revealed a generally positive attitude among both students and teachers towards the potential of podcasts for listening enhancement. Based on these findings, several recommendations are proposed to EFL teachers to assist in effectively utilizing podcasts in the EFL classrooms.

Keywords: Podcasts, Listening, EFL students, EFL teachers, Attitudes.

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List of Abbreviations

- **EFL** : English as a Foreign Language
- **ICT**: Information and Communication Technology
- **RSS** : Really Simple Syndication
- **MP3** : MPEG Audio Layer 3
- **MP4** : MPEG-4 Part 14
- **CLT** : Communicative Language Teaching
- **TBL** : Task-Based Learning
- **PC** : Personal Computer
- **PDF** : Portable Document Format
- **CALL** : Computer-Assisted Language Learning

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General

Introduction

General Introduction

Learning foreign languages poses a challenge for many learners, particularly when it comes to developing listening skills. This skill plays a vital role in foreign language acquisition. In this context, the use of new technologies and innovative teaching materials can bring significant benefits to language teaching and learning.

In the recent years, Information and Communication Technology (ICT) have become widely used in all areas of life, particularly in the field of education. Technological tools has progressed from the use of overhead transparencies to tablets, MP3 players, and interactive whiteboards, passing through the use of projectors, media, multimedia, and computers...

Podcasts are increasingly recognized as significant and widely utilized technological tools in teaching and learning, particularly within modern language education. A podcast is a digital program that can be downloaded in MP3 format or streamed online. Podcasts are also very different from traditional and contemporary radio programs. They are digital audio files, more akin to a series of radio broadcasts. Users can subscribe to their favorite podcasts and receive these audio programs regularly on a mobile device.

Listening comprehension is a necessary step in learning foreign languages because, to communicate, one must first understand. Recognizing this, we found it pertinent to explore a pedagogical tool in listening comprehension sessions to make learners more motivated and improve their performance in this skill.

Statement of the Problem:

Listening is an important language skill used to develop English language students in their foreign language learning. It is considered one of the most essential skills for language learners. In their daily lives, learners engage in listening for various purposes such as entertainment, news, and education. A form of digital audio content which is podcast, it has emerged as an effective tool for improving EFL students' listening comprehension.

Podcasts are one of the tools that can be an innovation in the teaching of listening. Their current popularity among learners stems from the wide-ranging topics they cover, including hobbies, daily activities, current news, food recipes, and much more. However, despite the accessibility and popularity of podcasts, we still lack extensive research on how

effective and well-received they are as a learning resource specifically for EFL students. Consequently, it's crucial to understand the attitudes of both EFL teachers and students regarding the use of podcasts as a teaching tool aimed at improving learners' listening skills.

Research Objectives:

1. To explore students' perceptions and attitudes regarding the use of podcasts as an educational resource to improve their listening skills.
2. To comprehend how EFL teachers perceive the usage of podcast as instructional tool.
3. To identify EFL teachers' attitudes towards the use of podcast as a tool for language instruction.

Research Questions:

1. What are the attitudes of EFL students towards using podcasts for improving their listening skills?
2. What are EFL teachers' perceptions and attitudes towards using podcasts as an instructional tool?

Research Design:

This study employed a qualitative approach to understand the attitudes of EFL teachers and third-year LMD students towards podcasts as an instructional material for enhancing students' listening skills at the Department of English Language, University of Relizane. Data collection was carried out through two structured questionnaires: one for EFL students and another for EFL teachers.

The students' questionnaire aimed to explore students' experiences with podcasts as a learning tool, their perceived benefits and challenges of using podcasts for enhancing their listening skills, their comfort levels and attitudes towards their integration into EFL classes, and their recommendations for more effective use. The questionnaire was distributed directly to a cohort of thirty-nine (39) third-year LMD students within the Department of English Language at the University of Relizane. The teachers' questionnaire was designed to gather data on teachers' familiarity with podcasts, their perceptions of the pedagogical value of podcasts for listening skill development, perceived benefits and challenges of their implementation, attitudes towards their integration into teaching practices, and suggestions

for effective utilization and necessary support. The questionnaire was administered to a sample of ten (10) EFL teachers within the Department of English Language at the University of Relizane. For practicality reasons and for teachers' convenience, the questionnaire was distributed and collected electronically via email through Google Forms.

Significance of the Study:

This study offers significant value to EFL education by exploring both students' and teachers' attitudes toward using podcasts as an instructional tool to enhance listening skills. The insights gained from understanding these attitudes, perceptions, and perspectives can be crucial for curriculum designers seeking to effectively integrate ICT tools, particularly podcasts, into language learning, ensuring alignment with the preferences of both teachers and students.

Structure of the Thesis:

This dissertation comprises two chapters, a theoretical part which represents the literature review, and a practical one. The theoretical chapter comprises two sections. The first section provides an overview of podcast including definition, features, benefits, and challenges in implementation. Special attention is given to podcasts in the EFL context. The section further includes podcasts as a language learning material, effectiveness of podcasts for listening skills, and general attitudes toward podcasts. The second section, however, focuses on the second variable, which is listening comprehension. It begins by defining listening skills, emphasizing the importance of listening skills, it provides the different stages, types. Following this, the discussion transitions to listening comprehension, exploring relevant approaches, difficulties that EFL learners may face during listening, and finishing by the importance of listening comprehension in EFL teaching and learning. The second chapter introduces the methodology used in this research. This chapter begins with the research design, settings, and followed by a representation of the participants and the data collection instruments used. Specifically, it interprets the data obtained from both the students' and the teachers' questionnaires. The data was analyzed using tables, pie charts, and graphs, followed by a discussion of the findings. This discussion leads to a proposition of some research recommendations. Finally, the research ends with limitations that hindered the investigation process.

Chapter One

**Podcasts as Instructional Material to
Enhance Listening Skills**

Chapter One: Podcast as Instructional Material to Enhance Listening Skills

Introduction

The integration of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in education has introduced powerful tools for language learning, with podcasts standing out as particularly impactful. According to Sullivan (2019), the most popular streaming media online currently are podcasts. Podcast is one of the most recent technological innovations language teachers use in their pedagogy. Several authors have discussed that podcasts will serve as a new source of exposure to the target language (Rosell-Aguilar, 2013).

Listening like other aspects of language (speaking, writing, and reading) is the basic skill for learning English. According to Nunan (1997), listening has long been considered “the Cinderella skill in second language learning” (p. 47).

This chapter systematically examines these concepts through two focused sections. The first section provides an overview of podcast including definition, features, benefits, and challenges in implementation. Special attention is given to podcasts in the EFL context. The section further includes podcasts as a language learning material, effectiveness of podcasts for listening skills, and general attitudes toward podcasts. The second section, however, focuses on the second variable, which is listening comprehension. It begins by defining listening skills, emphasizing the importance of listening skills, it provides the different stages, types, and then moving to listening comprehension, following it by approaches, difficulties that EFL learners may face during listening, and finishing by the importance of listening comprehension in EFL teaching and learning.

1.1 Podcasts

1.1.1 What are Podcasts?

Podcast was coined in 2004 by Ben Hammersley, it is a combination of the words "iPod" and "broadcast" (Hammersley, 2004). A podcast is essentially like a radio broadcast but one that you can download and hear whenever and wherever you prefer. It is an audio program and sometimes comes in video format. Podcasts are typically focused on some specific topics such as education, entertainment, etc., and offer new episodes regularly.

Constantine (2007) has defined a podcast as an online audio publication that is meant to be downloaded and listened to on a portable device like tablets, smartphones, and laptops. Similarly, according to Erben et al. (2008), a podcast is a digital file created and posted on the Internet and can be played on a mobile phone or a laptop whenever it is convenient for the listener.

Many researchers have characterized podcasts as audio file series (sometimes video) which are downloaded automatically through subscription to a Really Simple Syndication (RSS) feed (Cebeci and Tekdal, 2006; Selingo, 2006). This flexibility is a main advantage, as podcasts can be downloaded onto several devices, including laptops and smartphones, and enjoyed at anytime, at anywhere (Evans, 2008). Per Geoghegan and Klass (2005), podcasts exist as audio able to be accessed via the net that is automatically sent to a PC or MP3 player (p. 3).

Podcasts tend to be in MP3 format, plus easily downloadable. They can include audio, videos, lectures, images, PDFs, and text. They can include further file types (Morris, 2006). Levy (2009) provides a more wide-ranging definition of podcasting, calling it "an audio/video file that can be broadcast via the Internet with sound files that are 'pushed' to subscribers, often at regular intervals" (p. 775).

As per Sloan (2005), podcasting is an innovative way to casting over the Internet and can transmit digital audio content automatically to mobile phones. Gromik (2008) asserts that podcasting can provide students "access to authentic, free and otherwise unavailable" resources in non-English speaking contexts. Podcast users can access that information without great difficulty through their iPods, as well as computers (Benno, 2006). People are able to access files that they desire or require and view or hear them when convenient, wherever (Morris, 2006).

1.1.2 Dictionary Definitions of Podcasts

The Oxford Advanced American Dictionary (Oxford University Press, 2021) defines a podcast a broadcast radio recording or audio downloaded from the Internet. In another place, the Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary (10th ed., 2020), a podcast can mean a digital audio file that can be taken from the internet as well as played on a computer or a device that you can carry with you. Still, definitions shift; The New Oxford American

Dictionary (Oxford University Press, 2005) states that a podcast constitutes a downloadable digital audio file playable through a portable media player, smartphone, computer, etc.

1.1.3 Distinctive Features of Podcasts

Podcasts have original characteristics that set them apart from other online resources. As Stanely (2006) explains, "what sets podcasting apart from many other ways of delivering audio online, such as streaming, is the specific idea of automatically downloaded content". According to Stanely, what makes this possible is RSS (Really Simple Syndication). Likewise, Rosell-Aguilar (2007) particularly stresses one issue. "The fact that podcasting uses RSS is what differentiates it from simple downloading or streaming"(p. 472). The features, especially auto upgrades, let users join podcasts and get auto upgrades, making content delivery efficient plus user-friendly than standard ways.

1.1.4 Types of Podcasts

Podcasts vary in different types depending on the level and method of presentation. According to Salmon et al (2008), there are three main types of podcasts: audio podcasts, video podcasts and enhanced podcasts.

1.1.4.1 Audio Podcasts

Audio podcasts are the simplest to create because they only require a microphone and a few software applications for capturing and modifying (Rosell-Aguilar, 2007). Audio podcasts are easy to download at any internet speed as they have the smallest file size and are the easiest way to spread the message to listeners (Dennett et al., 2008), these files are available in multiple formats, with the most recognized being the MPEG Audio Layer 3 (MP3) format. Several audio podcasts in English can be found on Spotify, Google Podcasts, Apple Podcasts and others. According to Dennett et al. (2008), audio podcasts are the most popular source because they are accessible and easier to produce than video podcasts.

1.1.4.2 Video Podcasts

Video podcasts also known as vodcasts (Kay, 2012). This type is a video and sound in one structure, making them more engaging and suitable for instructional content like tutorials or demonstrations (Zahn et al., 2010). Video podcasts are usually in MP4 format and require

more storage than audio podcasts. Podcasts in the form of videos can be found through the YouTube application.

1.1.4.3. Enhanced Podcasts

Enhanced podcasts are standard audio podcasts that include additional features to assist audience members (Fernández et al., 2009). One instance of these features is incorporating a slideshow with accompanying audio (Lonn & Teasley, 2009). Thus, you can obtain the complete view. An additional feature is breaking the podcast into segments or chapters, thus allowing you to effortlessly locate and replay particular sections (Fernández et al., 2009). This assists listeners in exploring and discovering the data they require with greater ease.

In summary, various podcast types serve distinct purposes, with audio podcasts being the simplest to produce, video podcasts delivering visual appeal, and enhanced podcasts allowing for interactivity and extra educational resources.

1.1.5 Podcasts in the EFL Context

In today's technologically driven world, employing technology within education is important to achieving a lasting influence on how students acquire knowledge. Indeed, several newer web-based materials contribute greatly to EFL learning. These materials are podcasts (Farangi, Nejadghanbar, Askary, & Ghorbani, 2015). Precisely, podcasts provide accessibility to multiple themes, accents, terms, and spoken language, rendering them an essential resource for EFL students.

In addition, in the EFL context, podcasts are viewed as a way of providing educational content through technology to greatly strengthen individuals' educational experiences (Jain & Hashmi, 2013). Regarding frequency of usage, Constantine (2007) stresses that always even podcasts can assist certain EFL learners at only the beginner level when heard six minutes daily. This limited, but constant, unveiling, he claims, can considerably increase language learning and greatly develop listening confidence levels. Inside of the language classroom, podcasts let several different students to understand content, as well as improve their listening comprehension, also become more skilled. Furthermore, the integration of podcasts into EFL instruction matches the greater focus upon tech-based learning, offering teachers fresh ways of increasing learner participation.

Adding to these benefits, Rahim and Katal (2012) affirmed that the use of podcasts in the EFL classroom promotes motivation in learners fully, and involvement, largely since tasks using podcasts make students try harder with the language as well as create their speeches. This overall increased engagement can be attributed to the largely natural accessibility of podcasts. Consequently, certain students can understand course content more rapidly when they listen throughout podcasts than when they read across the content of a speech (Rajic, 2013).

In conclusion, podcasts act as a special resource in the EFL context, providing learners as well as teachers with an engaging and it is a flexible approach to language study. Podcasts, overall, connect classroom learning and real-world language use by presenting authentic language material, into multiple inflections, and with real-world communication scenarios.

1.1.6 Podcasts as Language Learning Material

Digital technologies refer to electronic tools, systems, and devices, while digital learning materials encompass any type of educational content that uses technology as its medium or source (Tomlinson, 2011). These digital learning materials represent any educational content delivered through technological means, ranging from traditional computers to modern mobile devices (Warschauer, 2007). The form of digital learning material can be in the form of audio, visual, and audiovisual. One of the digital learning materials in an audiovisual form is the podcast.

Podcasts have gained increasing recognition as valuable resources in language learning due to their flexibility, accessibility, and diversity of content. Rosell-Aguilar (2007) suggests that available podcast resources for language learners can be broadly categorized into two main groups. The first group consists of authentic content provided by native speakers or advanced learners, not specifically intended for language teaching. These podcasts often cover subjects such as news, football or radio programming. The second group includes language courses or teaching content specifically designed for educational purposes. This category can be further divided into two subgroups: materials created for a known audience, such as recordings produced by teachers, institutions, or students for use in their classes featuring elements like oral quizzes, vocabulary lists, feedback and materials aimed at independent learners, made available as public podcasts for general language improvement.

In conclusion, podcasts have emerged as an important component of digital learning materials, offering EFL learners a flexible and engaging way to access educational content. The podcast can be a source of digital learning material because it involves rich material from many fields (Evans, 2008).

1.1.7 The Benefits of Podcasts

According to studies and literature sources, podcasts offer several benefits in teaching English as a Foreign Language (EFL). Specifically, podcasting can be used to enhance listening skills of students. For example, podcasts introduce learners to different topics, diverse accents, and real communication. Consequently, this exposure helps students improve their listening skills. Indeed, studies have shown that students who regularly listen to podcasts experience improvements in their listening comprehension and feel more confident in understanding spoken English (Djellouli & Elalia, 2023; Wardana, 2024). Moreover, accessibility has been included among the most important advantages. The student can listen to podcasts anywhere and everywhere it is convenient for them because they can be streamed via a range of devices, including smartphones (Rahman et al., 2018). In fact, because of their mobility, podcasts are a perfect learning device, particularly for students who might not have access to conventional language learning. Moreover, there are some free learning podcasts offered on apps like Spotify, Apple Podcasts, and YouTube, which offers an affordable resource for students with limited budgets (Lauer, 2018). In addition to these benefits, podcasting is also able to improve students' motivation in the EFL context. Since it provides free, authentic, and accessible materials and offers various interesting topics to be learned, podcasts can increase students' interest in the language, making learning feel more relevant and enjoyable. The variety of topics available also helps maintain a sense of novelty and excitement in the learning process, fostering a positive learning environment (Moussaoui, 2019). Another important advantage of podcasts is their flexibility. Many researchers have highlighted this benefit, emphasizing the ease with which authentic podcasts can be downloaded and accessed anytime and anywhere. The flexibility gives it an ease to incorporate learning into day-to-day activities so that students can fit language practice into their hectic lives (Evans, 2008). Also, learners can access material without an uninterrupted internet connection because they can download podcasts to play offline (Read, 2007). So, because they are so straightforward and flexible as part of them, podcasts make a great device for students who have non-conventional schedules as well as self-study. Finally, and

importantly, podcasts are cost effective. Unlike paid courses or textbooks, most podcasts are free, reducing financial barriers for students who want to improve their English (Mohammed & Khadawardi, 2024). Even when subscription-based, they are more affordable compared to traditional language-learning materials. Podcasts are generally free or low-cost and can be accessed on a wide range of devices, including smartphones, tablets, and computers (Salmon et al., 2008).

1.1.8 Challenges of Podcasts in the EFL Environment

Podcasts have become a popular teaching medium in the EFL environment; they have a number of drawbacks that may reduce their usefulness. It is essential for educators who want to maximize their teaching practices to comprehend these disadvantages.

First, technological and connectivity issues are serious barriers. A reliable internet connection is required to access and utilize podcasts effectively. Internet connectivity issues can interfere with learning and reduce the enthusiasm of students in the subject (Suseno, 2024). In addition, all students may not be able to use tools like Google Meet and WhatsApp to disperse podcasts, which could lead to unequal participation and access.

Second, learner engagement and motivation can be significantly impacted. EFL students tend to struggle with staying motivated, which can affect their active participation in podcasting tasks (Pakpahan, 2023). Anxiety and cultural backgrounds may also deter student engagement, particularly in speaking tasks that may force students to interact with the recorded content (Husamaddin, 2024).

Thirdly, Pedagogical considerations are necessary for successful podcast integration. Effective instructional approaches such as Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) and Task-Based Learning (TBL) that encourage speaking skills and active learning are imperative. To develop students' confidence and dispel any fears they may have, teachers must change their style to break language barriers and offer positive reinforcement (Suseno, 2024; Husamaddin, 2024).

Finally, it is important to remember that even though podcasts are a popular tool in EFL teaching, there are some real challenges that can get in the way of using them effectively. One big issue is accessibility. You see, a lot of students rely on having a good internet connection to access podcasts, and if that connection is unreliable, as Yasmiatun

(2023) points out, it can seriously limit their ability to engage with the material. There is also the problem of device availability; not all students have the smartphones or other gadgets they need to listen to podcasts, and that creates inequality, as Yasmiatun (2023) also noted. Another challenge is the overwhelming amount of content available. With so many podcasts to choose from, students can easily become confused while trying to find relevant and high-quality material, which may reduce the effectiveness of their learning (Yasmiatun, 2023).

In conclusion, while podcasts have established themselves as valuable tools in EFL learning, their limitations mean they are not always the perfect solution. Educators who want to improve their teaching should definitely keep these limitations in mind.

1.1.9 Effectiveness of Podcasts for Listening Skills

Several studies revealed significant impacts on students' development of listening skills. Podcasts have proven effective in improving listening comprehension, supported by both quantitative and qualitative findings. Firstly, podcasts offer authentic language input, exposing learners to natural speech patterns, varied accents, and real-world language use. Studies conducted in Algeria (Benkaret, 2024; Moussaoui, 2019), Saudi Arabia (Mohammed & Khadawardi, 2024), and Indonesia (Rahman et al., 2018) have highlighted how podcasts enhance listening comprehension by immersing students in authentic contexts. Secondly, experimental research underscores significant gains in listening comprehension. For instance, Rahman et al. (2018) reported higher test scores in a podcast group compared to a control group. Similarly, Djellouli & Elalia (2023) found that students who listened to podcasts got much better at picking out important information and understanding new words in spoken English. Furthermore, Abdulrahman et al. (2018) demonstrated that podcasts significantly improved students' listening comprehension and increased their motivation. Their study showed that students were enthusiastic about using podcasts in the listening classroom. They were more motivated to learn English because podcasts provided realistic materials and engaging activities, such as listening exercises and meaningful tasks. Beyond listening comprehension, podcasts offer additional benefits, including improved vocabulary acquisition, pronunciation, and overall confidence in understanding spoken English. This was evident in studies by Benkaret (2024) and NurCahyanti (2023), where learners reported greater familiarity with idiomatic expressions and contextual language. Finally, real-world application is further supported by the findings of Al Qasim and Al Fadda (2013), who observed significant improvements in listening skills and increased motivation among

students in a Saudi language college who utilized podcasts in their learning. These findings highlight the important role podcasts play in supporting English language learning by offering an engaging, accessible, and effective platform for language development.

1.1.10 General Attitudes of EFL Students and Teachers toward Podcasts

Studies reveal that both students and teachers hold generally positive attitudes toward using podcasts in English as a Foreign Language (EFL) learning contexts. Indeed, podcasts are perceived as innovative, engaging tools that foster autonomous learning and enhance language skills (Daouadi&Bounoua, 2023; Moussaoui, 2019; Djellouli, 2023). Furthermore, learners appreciate their flexibility, allowing for self-paced learning and replaying specific segments to aid comprehension. For instance, students in Algeria (Djellouli&Elalia, 2023) and Saudi Arabia (Mohammed &Khadawardi, 2024) viewed podcasts as useful tools that made learning English more enjoyable. This positive view was echoed in study conducted in Indonesia (NurCahyanti, 2023), where podcasts helped sustain learners' motivation and encouraged self-paced learning. Moreover, teachers appreciate podcasts as a resource to provide authentic language input, promote learner autonomy, and diversify classroom activities. However, some educators noted a lack of familiarity with integrating podcasts into the curriculum, which limits their adoption (Lauer, 2018). Nevertheless, teachers have highlighted their utility in providing diverse content tailored to students' needs, which motivates learners to engage more deeply with language material (Sičová, 2022). Reinforcing this positive trend, a study by Menezes and Morera (2009) in Portugal found that 7th graders enjoyed using podcasts, saying it made them more motivated. Similarly, Kavaliauskienė and Anusienė (2009) surveyed students at Mykolas Romeris University in Lithuania about using podcasts for listening practice. They found that a large majority (76%) of the students were enthusiastic about the idea, seeing real potential in podcasts for improving their listening skills.

In conclusion, the use of podcasts in teaching has shown to be more effective than traditional methods. Numerous studies have demonstrated their ability to enhance learning, increase motivation, and improve academic performance. As a result, Podcasts are a powerful tool of learning. Accordingly, the findings of the studies have revealed the positive attitudes of both learners and teachers toward the integration of podcasting into the learning process.

1.2. Listening Skills

1.2.1 Definition of Listening

In terms of language learning, listening is one of the four essential language skills every learner should master. According to Zhdanov and Baklanov (2020), the term "listening" traditionally refers to the complex process of perceiving and understanding spoken language, whereas "hearing" is viewed more as an acoustic sense of speech. Hamouda (2013) defines listening as the process of identifying and comprehending speakers' messages to enable later reproduction of the heard content. Rost (2011) describes listening as a process where an individual receives what is said by a speaker and constructs meaning through active involvement, imagination, and empathetic response.

Based on Brown, as cited in Bozorgian (2012), the fundamental skill of acquiring a language is listening, yet it is rarely explored and comprehended. Cameron (2001) revealed that listening is the receptive use of language, and since the aim is understanding speech so, meaning is given importance over language. Underwood (1989) similarly focuses on the intentional aspect, defining listening as the activity of paying attention to and trying to get meaning from something we hear.

Purdy and Borisoff (1997) further elaborate that listening is the active and dynamic process of attending, perceiving, interpreting, remembering, and responding to the verbal and nonverbal needs, concerns, and information expressed by others. The Oxford Dictionary (1993) expands this further by characterizing listening as a complex, problem-solving skill that extends beyond sound perception to encompass comprehension of linguistic units from words to extended discourse. It is regarded as a passive skill but it is actually an active process "Listening, like all acts of perception, is a dynamic, active process involving the communicator and the recipient" (Steinberg, 2007, p.75).

1.2.2 The Importance of Listening

One of the most crucial English language skills is listening, particularly in the context of second language acquisition. Developing this skill is fundamental for mastering a new language (Rost, 1994). Listening skill is one of the most important aspects of language learning and teaching. In language learning process, it is a requirement for speaking skill. That is why, listening skill can be considered as a significant skill in oral production, since it

lays the foundation for communication (Yavuz, & Celik, 2017). Without this skill, students struggle to participate actively in language activities. The primacy of listening is evident from childhood development as Lundsteen (1979) notes, it is the first language skill to emerge, with children naturally listening before speaking.

According to Shariyevna (2020), listening is important in both daily life and educational ones. In daily communication, listening occupies 45% of interaction time (Hedge, 2000), highlighting its indispensable role in both social and educational contexts. Rost (2016) further asserts that communication itself depends on listening, which not only completes the communicative process but also shapes interpretation and impact. Beyond functionality, listening exposes learners to authentic language patterns, including pronunciation, intonation, and vocabulary, facilitating incidental acquisition (Field, 2009). Rost (2002) adds that proficient listening enhances cognitive growth, information processing, and learner autonomy. Podcasts, as authentic audio resources, amplify these benefits by offering real-world accents, speech rates, and conversational styles—exposure often absent in textbooks—thus bridging classroom learning and real-life communication (Hedge, 2000).

In conclusion, listening is a foundation of language learning and communication. By improved listening ability, learners can optimize their comprehension, participate in meaningful interactions, learn authentic pronunciation and vocabulary usage habits, and develop greater learner independence and mental competence.

1.2.3 Stages of the Listening Process

According to Tyagi (2013), the process of listening occurs in five stages, they are: hearing, understanding, remembering, evaluating, and responding.

1.2.3.1 Hearing

Hearing is the initial stage of the listening process, involving the physical act of perceiving sound through our ears. It is a physiological process whereby sensory receptors receive auditory stimuli. However, listening requires more than hearing; it demands focused attention and selective perception. The brain screens out distracting stimuli to focus on specific messages, both verbal and nonverbal. Responding with feedback is essential to confirm successful communication. Without attention and feedback, the process of active listening cannot be completed.

1.2.3.2 Understanding

Understanding is the stage where students attempt to comprehend the meaning behind the sounds that they hear. It is not just hearing sounds — it is actively processing words, tone, and context to get the message. Listeners must focus, decode words, notice nonverbal cues, and interpret the speaker's intent. It involves actively interpreting and processing the information gathered through listening. The meaning attached to symbols is a function of association in the past and the context in which the symbols appear. It is important for the listener to understand both the intended meaning and the context assumed by the sender to create successful interpersonal communication.

1.2.3.3 Remembering

Remembering is an important step in the listening process because it demonstrates that a person has taken in, processed, and stored the data in their memory. When listening, memory and attention are both selective and may not match what was initially seen or heard.

1.2.3.4 Evaluating

Evaluating is like a judgment of what has been said and this is often related to the listener prior knowledge. In this stage of listening, active listeners critically evaluate and analyze the information they have heard. Effective listeners won't begin this action too soon because it demands stopping listening to the current communication and turning your attention to the incoming message, which stops the listening process.

1.2.3.5 Responding

Responding is the final stage of the listening process is known as reaction, or feedback, where listeners respond to the message they have received. It involves checking if the message has been received correctly through asking some questions or reforming it in another way. This stage is crucial, as it enables the sender to assess whether the message was successfully understood. Without responding, the sender has no reliable way to evaluate the effectiveness of the communication.

1.2.4 Types of Listening

There are two different types of listening which are, intensive and extensive listening

1.2.4.1 Intensive Listening

Intensive listening refers to structured classroom activities designed to develop learners' awareness of specific linguistic elements (Rost, 2006). Unlike extensive listening, which occurs naturally outside class, intensive listening requires teacher guidance and typically involves follow-up tasks like note-taking (Harmer, 2007). This concentrated approach targets phonological, syntactic, and lexical features, demanding careful attention to detail (Yıldırım & Yıldırım, 2016). As Hasan and Nomnian (2021) emphasize, intensive listening promotes language-focused learning, essential for sustained acquisition. The teacher plays a central role in providing feedback and ensuring accuracy throughout these focused listening exercises.

1.2.4.2 Extensive listening

Extensive listening, unlike its intensive counterpart, typically occurs outside formal classroom settings and emphasizes enjoyable, prolonged exposure to authentic language (Canpolat et al., 2015). This approach prioritizes global comprehension over linguistic details, fostering overall understanding and critical thinking through real-life speech contexts. Teachers facilitate extensive listening by curating suitable materials such as podcasts that develop learners' exposure to diverse accents and vocabulary (Harmer, 2007). By engaging with varied linguistic inputs, learners naturally enhance their ability to extract meaning from different language varieties while improving pronunciation recognition and vocabulary acquisition. The cumulative effect of this immersive practice significantly boosts listening proficiency through sustained, meaningful exposure.

1.2.5 Listening Comprehension

1.2.5.1 Definition

Before defining listening comprehension, it is necessary to define the term comprehension first. According to Wang and Gafurov (2015), comprehension is identified as the ability to understand something, reflecting an intelligent capacity for abstract thought and reasoning. Similarly, Comprehension has been described by Durkin (1973) as “active and intentional thinking in which the meaning is constructed”. Those definitions share the same opinion that the comprehension of something means understanding thought and that it is an intelligent process

Listening comprehension has defined by many researchers. Xuyen (2020) sees it as an interactive process in which listeners are involved in constructing meaning. Sulton et al. (2021) point out the different cognitive mechanisms involved in processing spoken language. Gilakjani and Ahmadi (2011) refer to it as a process that relies on contextual information and general knowledge. Finally, El-dali (2017) notes that listening comprehension operates as a top-down process, which means that the different types of knowledge used to understand language are not used in any particular order.

Listening comprehension needs certain techniques and mental processes that allow people to be good listeners, those processes are top-down processing and bottom-up processing.

1.2.6 The Listening Comprehension Processes

Effective listening comprehension in EFL learning is shaped by two main processing approaches. They are top-down process and bottom-up process (Nation & Newton, 2009). Each approach represents a different way learners make sense of spoken language.

1.2.6.1 The Bottom up Process

The bottom-up approach to listening was introduced by researchers between the 1940s and 1950s, views listening as a systematic decoding process where understanding builds progressively from small linguistic units to complete messages (Buck, 2000). From this perspective, listeners first identify distinct sounds (phonemes), then combine them to create words, phrases, and eventually complete sentences in order to gain meaning - a strictly linear process in which meaning arises as the final product (Nunan, 2002). Flowerdew and Miller explained the bottom-up processing in a more analytical way and claimed:

“Listeners build understanding by starting with the smallest units of the acoustic message: individual sounds, or phonemes. These are then combined into words, which, in turn, together make up phrases, clauses, and sentences. Finally, individual sentences combine to create ideas and concepts and relationships between them.” (2005, p. 24)

Batova (2013) emphasizes this decoding factor, noting that “bottom-up processing involves segmenting individual words out of the stream of speech” (p. 3). This is most

beneficial to listening accuracy acquisition because it helps learners with separating similar sounds, hearing word boundaries, and understanding grammatical forms in speech.

1.2.6.2 The Top Down Process

The top-down approach to listening focuses on how listeners use their background knowledge, expectations, and understanding of the context to make sense of what they hear.

Many researchers define this process in different ways. Newton (2008) describes this process as one where listeners predict the content of a message based on the situation, and then use parts of what they hear to confirm, correct, or expand their understanding. He points out that inferencing drawing conclusions from limited information is at the heart of this approach (p. 40). In a similar way, Batova (2013) define it as “emphasizing the listeners use of their existing knowledge of a topic and the relevant context in forming hypotheses as to the speakers meaning and, when appropriate, in modifying them to match new incoming information” (p.4).

What makes this approach special is how it helps us in real-life situations. As Vandergrift and Goh (2012) point out, it is all about using context and what we already know to understand messages (p. 18). This is why we can still follow conversations even when we miss some words - our brain fills in the gaps using our knowledge of how conversations usually work.

Effective listeners do not rely on just one approach - they skillfully combine both bottom-up and top-down strategies. Peterson (2001) explains this dynamic interaction well, noting that “in proficient listeners, top-down and bottom-up processes interact, so that lack of information at one level can be compensated for by checking against information at the other level”(89).

1.2.7 Listening Difficulties

Listening comprehension poses significant difficulties for EFL students due to various factors. Understanding these challenges is crucial for designing effective listening instruction and support strategies.

One major barrier is the difficulty to distinguish sounds. One of the problems that EFL students have is distinguishing sounds and boundaries in the stream of speech (Shelton,

2008), learners might not distinguish between sounds such as words like “right”, “write” or “their”, “there”. As a result, students cannot interpret the sound accurately.

Another barrier is unfamiliar vocabulary and complex grammar structures. When learners encounter unknown words or difficult sentence patterns, it interrupts their understanding and forces them to focus more on decoding than on meaning (Graham, 2006). Accents and pronunciation variations also present difficulties, especially when learners are used to only one form of English and then encounter different regional or international varieties.

Difficulty to concentrate, it is caused by some factors. One of them is that the learners are not interested with the materials of listening. Another one is the unfamiliarity with sounds, sentences and terms. When the student is not interested or is not familiar with materials, he / she will consider that the materials are difficult. It is tiring for learner to concentrate on interpreting unfamiliar sounds, sentences and words for long periods (Yagang, 2008).

Speed of speech is yet another common challenge. Many EFL students lament not being able to keep up with native or near-native speakers who speak quickly, use reductions, or blend words together naturally. Therefore, they have to accustom to the native speed of speech.

Psychological problems like anxiety, lack of motivation, and low confidence level can significantly influence listening performance (Goh, 2000). Students can become easily discouraged if they are not able to understand sounds and words, which leads to frustration and disengagement.

Ur (1989) points out several difficulties: (1) hearing the sounds; (2) understanding intonations and stress; (3) coping with redundancy and noise; (4) predicting; (5) understanding vocabulary; (6) understanding different accents; (7) not using visual or environment clues; (8) fatigue. Besides those eight factors based on Gilakjani & Sabouri (2016) statement, Nushi & Orouji (2020) added that accents, cultural differences, and the length of listening can be problems in listening comprehension.

1.2.8 The Importance of Listening Comprehension in EFL Teaching and Learning

Listening comprehension is a fundamental skill in language learning and is central to the success of English as a Foreign Language (EFL) teaching and learning. According to Rost (1994), listening is essential in foreign language instruction because it provides learners with input—without understanding what they hear, learning simply cannot happen. When learning a second or a foreign language, listening is important because it gives learners the sounds of the language, which is the base for building all other language abilities. Listening comprehension stands as a cornerstone in the process of acquiring a second or foreign language. As asserted by Ranukadevi (2014), listening assumes paramount importance in English learning, being one of the pillars cardinal to linguistic competence acquisition.

Modi (1991) also argued that listening is where language learning starts. It's how we pick up on how words should sound, the right accent, and all those tiny changes in someone's voice that change the meaning. Listening helps us tell sounds apart, get a handle on how sentences work, and, most importantly, actually understand what people are trying to say – the ideas, the feelings, everything.

Listening is especially important in education, as it is the main method students use to absorb information at all levels of learning (Gilakjani & Ahmadi, 2011, p. 979). Nunan (1997, as cited in Khaled, 2010) also pointed out that listening comprehension is not an easy skill, but it is a very complicated and very necessary process, playing a vital role in both first and second language acquisition. Listening is taking more attention in the EFL classroom context since it is important to develop the students' communicative competence which is one of the main goals the students want to achieve.

Despite its importance, listening is often overlooked in language research. Richards and Renandya (2002) noted that listening is the most commonly used skill in language learning, yet it remains the least studied. Still, it plays a key role in language development when learners are exposed to the right kind of input. Listening is not only a part of communication, but a primary means through which people spend most of their time interacting with others.

Conclusion

This theoretical chapter has provided a comprehensive review of the listening skill and podcasts, establishing a foundation for exploring their intersection in language learning. The first section highlighted podcasts, tracing their definition, features, and various types. It also discussed podcasts in the EFL context, outlining their benefits as well as challenges, including technical issues and the need to select appropriate content. In addition, the section also addressed podcasts as educational resource, their effectiveness on the development of listening skills, and general attitudes towards podcasts. The second section offered an insightful overview of listening skills emphasizing their importance, the stages of listening, different types of listening, and the difficulties students commonly encounter. In the next chapter of this research, we will focus on the practical part of investigating students' and teachers' attitudes towards podcasts as instructional material and how it improves students' listening skills.

Chapter Two

**Research Methodology and Data
Analysis**

Chapter Two: Research Methodology and Data Analysis

Introduction

This chapter describes the research methods and procedures used to investigate the attitudes of EFL teachers and students toward the use of podcasts as instructional material to enhance listening skills. It begins by outlining the rationale behind the research design, followed by a description of the research settings. Next, it provides a representation of the participants including both student and teacher participants. Subsequently, the data collection instruments, namely the students' and teachers' questionnaires, are described. Finally, the chapter concludes by detailing the data analysis process and presenting the results of the students' and teachers' questionnaire analysis.

2.1. Research Design

This research investigates both teachers' and students' attitudes towards the use of podcasts as instructional material to enhance students' listening skills in EFL classrooms. The study employs a qualitative approach, utilizing qualitative data collection instruments, specifically students' questionnaires and teachers' questionnaires. This method allows for the exploration of the personal experiences, benefits, challenges, perceptions, and attitudes of both EFL teachers and students regarding the use of podcasts and their impact on listening skills. By focusing on these in-depth perspectives, the research aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of how podcasts influence listening comprehension and to assess the attitudes of both students and teachers towards podcasts as a tool for language learning.

2.2. Research Settings

This study was conducted during the 2024/2025 academic year within the English Department, Faculty of Letters and Languages, at the University of Relizane.

2.3. Participants

This study involved two distinct groups of participants: third-year EFL students and EFL teachers, both drawn from the Department of English Language at the University of Relizane.

2.3.1. The Students

This study was conducted during the 2024/2025 academic year with third-year students from the English Department at the University of Relizane. While the total population of third-year EFL students exceeds 100, this investigation involved 39 participants. The students were selected using convenience sampling, with no regards to their age, gender, or social status and also without taking any consideration their knowledge with the use of Podcasts. The reason for choosing this population is because they are at a level where language skills improvement is particularly needed, and because they were deemed the most suitable participants for the research objectives.

2.3.2 The Teachers:

This study included a sample of 10 EFL teachers from the English Department at the University of Relizane. These teachers were selected randomly to participate in this research and without taking into consideration their knowledge about the Podcasts use.

2.4 Data Collection Instruments

To gather the necessary data, two instruments were employed: the first, a student questionnaire, was distributed to 39 third-year EFL students in the English Department at Relizane University. The second type of our instrument is also a questionnaire but this one is made for 10 EFL teachers at the same university.

2.4.1 Students' Questionnaire

Because we were interested in students' perceptions and attitudes towards podcasts, the appropriate data collection instruments were either interviews or questionnaires. Since we had a large sample size, interviews were not suitable. Hence, the questionnaire was the most practical instrument which provides us with clear insights. The students' questionnaire, administered to 39 third-year LMD students in the English Department at the University of Relizane. It is made up of twenty three (23) questions written in English. The questionnaire consists of mainly three sections. It includes close-ended questions as well as open-ended questions. The questions varied from choosing "yes" or "no" options, multiple choices, ranking the answer and allowing participants to write their own responses. In general, the students' questionnaire will give us an idea about the students' familiarity with podcasts.

The questions are categorized into three sections. The first section deals with Background Information, it contains two questions that cover general information about the students' gender and age. The second section, General Consumption of Podcasts, this section contains nine questions designed to gather information about respondents' general podcast listening habits. It covers topics such as frequency of podcast use, preferred devices, typical listening duration, language preferences, preferred podcast formats and genres, whether they use podcasts for English language learning, and if so, their preferred type for language learning. The third section, Attitudes Towards Podcasts, explores students' perceptions and experiences with using podcasts, particularly for English language learning. This section investigates: prior experience with podcasts in the classroom (whether teachers have used podcasts as a teaching tool and, if so, the students' experience with it); beliefs about the benefits of podcasts (students' opinions on whether podcasts can enhance listening skills and which skills they believe are most improved); perceived effectiveness and comfort level (how effective students find podcasts for improving listening skills and how comfortable they are using them for learning); perceived advantages and challenges (students' views on the benefits and challenges of using podcasts for language learning); likes and recommendations (what students appreciate most about using podcasts for learning and whether they would recommend them for EFL classes); and suggestions for improvement (students' ideas on how to make podcasts more effective for language learning).

2.4.2 Teachers' Questionnaire

Due to our specific interest in understanding EFL teachers' perceptions and attitudes towards podcasts, the most appropriate data collection instruments considered were either interviews or questionnaires. Opting for a questionnaire was strategically chosen for particular reasons, primarily teacher convenience and logistical practicality. Given the demands on teachers' time, a self-administered questionnaire allowed them to provide detailed insights at their own convenience. This approach also facilitated the collection of data from the intended sample effectively. Thus, a questionnaire was deemed the most practical instrument for gathering clear and comprehensive insights. The questionnaire is divided into four sections. It contains sixteen (16) questions written in English. The questionnaire consists of mainly four sections. The first section deals with Background Information, it contains three questions that cover general information about the teachers' gender, age and years of teaching experience. The second section titled General Use of Podcasts, this section explores the teachers' personal use of podcasts and their experience

with using podcasts as a teaching tool in EFL classes. The third section, Attitudes Towards Podcasts, this section investigates the teachers' beliefs and perceptions about the effectiveness of podcasts in enhancing students' listening skills, their comfort level with integrating podcasts into teaching materials, and their views on the benefits and challenges of using podcasts in EFL teaching. The last section, Support, Training, and Recommendations , this section focuses on the support and resources teachers need to use podcasts effectively, their recommendations for using podcasts as a teaching tool, and their suggestions for making podcasts more effective in EFL teaching.

2.5 Data Analysis and Interpretation

This section details the analysis procedures employed for both the student and teacher questionnaires. Quantitative data, obtained from closed-ended questions in both questionnaires, was analyzed using descriptive statistics to determine frequencies and percentages. Qualitative data, gathered from open-ended questions, was subjected to a manual thematic analysis. This manual analysis, conducted without the use of computer software, involved a careful and systematic reading of the responses from both the student and teacher questionnaires to identify recurring themes, ideas, and opinions.

2.5.1 Students' Questionnaire

This analysis focuses on the students' questionnaire, which was distributed to 39 students in the English Department at Relizane University. The questionnaire comprised three sections, and its analysis is structured as follows:

A. Section One: Background Information

1. Question One: Students' gender

Figure 1: Students' Gender Distribution

The selected sample in this study shows that 77% of participants are females, whereas only 23% are males. This significant imbalance between the two genders is representative of the nature of the population of EFL students as a whole in the department of English in Relizane University.

2. Question Two: Students' age.

Table 1: Students' Age Distribution

Age	20 years old	21 years old	22 years old	Total
N°	22	13	4	39
%	57%	33%	10%	100%

The age distribution of the student participants in this study reveals that the majority are 20 years old, accounting for 57% of the sample. A significant portion, 33%, are 21 years old, the remaining 10% of participants are 22 years old. The age distribution shows that most of the participants in this study are quite close in age. This suggests that the students are likely in the same academic level or year of study.

B. Section Two: General Consumption of Podcasts

3. **Question Three:** Do you listen to podcasts? If no, please skip to part C.

Figure 2: Students' Use of Podcasts

It is clear from Figure 02 that the majority of participants, 95%, reported that they listen to podcasts, indicating a high level of familiarity and engagement with this medium. Only 5% of respondents stated that they do not listen to podcasts and were directed to skip to part C of the questionnaire. This demonstrates a high prevalence of podcast consumption within the student sample.

4. **Question Four:** How often do you listen to podcasts?

Table 2: Students' Frequency of Podcast Consumption

Options	Never	Rarely	Occasionally	Frequently	Always	Total
N°	0	9	18	6	4	37
%	0%	24%	49%	16%	11%	100%

The results from asking the learners about the frequency of listening to podcasts showed that 49% of them occasionally did, 24% rarely, 16% frequently, and 11% always

listened to podcasts. These results reinforce the previous questions results which is the degree of familiarity of the participants with Podcasts.

5. Question Five: Which device do you mostly use to access podcasts?

Figure 3: Podcast Access Devices

Regarding the device used to access podcasts. The results reveal that all participants (100%) reported using their smartphones as the primary device for listening to podcasts. This finding clearly shows that smartphones are the most preferred and accessible device among students for consuming podcast content.

6. Question Six: On average, how much time do you spend listening to podcasts per session?

Table 3: Distribution of Podcast Session Lengths

Options	N°	%
More than 30 minutes	16	43%
15 to 30 minutes.	12	33%
Less than 15 minutes	9	24%
Total	37	100%

When we look at table 03, we see that the duration of podcast listening sessions varied among the students. The largest group of the participants 43% reported spending more than 30 minutes per podcast session. While 33% of the learners spend 15–30 minutes per session. Meanwhile, 24% of respondents spend less than 15 minutes per session. These findings highlight the diverse ways in which students engage with podcasts, with a notable preference for longer listening sessions among the majority.

7. Question Seven: In what language(s) are the podcasts you listen to? (Select all the ones that apply ranking them with 1 being the common one)

Table 4: Podcast Language Distribution

Language	Ranking (1 = Most Common)	Percentage of Students
English	1	76%
Arabic	2	21%
French	3	3%

The results show that English is the most common language for podcasts, with 76% of students ranking it as their top choice (Rank 1). Arabic follows as the second most common language, selected by 21% of students (Rank 2), while French is the least common, chosen by only 3% of students (Rank 3). These findings highlight the dominance of English-language podcasts among students, with Arabic being a secondary preference and French being rarely used.

8. Question eight: Which podcast format do you enjoy the most? (Select as many that apply ranking them with 1 being the most listened to)

Figure 4: Most Enjoyed Podcast Formats Among Students

It is clear from the figure above that there is a distinct preference for certain podcast formats among the respondents. Interview Podcasts were ranked first by 35% of respondents, Solo (Monologue) Podcasts were ranked first by 23%, Conversational (Co-hosted) Podcasts and Narrative Storytelling (Fiction) each received 11% of the top ranking, Narrative Storytelling (Nonfiction) and Educational & How-To Podcasts were ranked first by 5% of respondents each, and News & Current Events, Panel Discussions, and Documentary-Style Podcasts each received 3% of the top ranking. These results indicate that there is a clear distribution among podcast format preferences, with interview and solo podcasts being the most listened podcast formats, which suggest that listeners mostly prefer podcasts that contain interviews and monologues, while other formats appear to be less preferred.

9. **Question nine:** Which podcast genre do you enjoy the most? (Select as many as apply and rank them starting with 1 being the most listened to)

Table 5: Most Enjoyed Podcast Genres Among Students

Podcast genre	Ranking (1 = Most Common)	N°	%
Self-Improvement & Productivity	1	17	46%
Comedy	2	5	14%
True Crime	3	4	11%
Business & Finance	4	3	8%
Health & Wellness	5	2	5%
History	6	2	5%
Hobbies & Niche Interests	7	2	5%
Science & Nature	8	1	3%
Pop Culture & Entertainment	9	1	3%
Technology	10	0	0%

As illustrated in the table above, the podcast genre preferences, ranked by 'most listened to', show the following distribution: Self-Improvement & Productivity was ranked first by 46% of respondents, Comedy by 14%, True Crime by 11%, Business & Finance by 8%, Health & Wellness by 5%, History by 5%, Hobbies & Niche Interests by 5%, Science & Nature by 3%, Pop Culture & Entertainment by 3%, and Technology by 0%. This distribution indicates a strong preference for Self-Improvement & Productivity podcasts, suggesting listeners are highly interested in content related to personal growth and efficiency. Comedy and True Crime also show notable levels of primary engagement. In contrast, genres like Technology received no top rankings within these students.

10. Question ten: Do you listen to podcasts to learn English?

Figure 5: Podcasts for English Learning

As shown in Figure 05, a substantial majority of the participants indicated that they listen to podcasts specifically for the purpose of learning English. The majority of students, 86%, reported that they listen to podcasts to learn English which means they are using podcasts as an English learning tool. On the other hand, 14% of respondents stated that they do not use podcasts for English learning. These results highlight the popularity of podcasts as a resource for English language learning among the majority of students.

11. Question eleven: Which type of podcast do you prefer for learning English?

Table 6: Preferred Podcast Types for English Language Learning

Podcasts Type	N°	%
Audio podcasts	11	30%
Video podcasts	18	49%
Enhanced podcasts	8	21%
Total	37	100%

As it can be seen from the table 06, students expressed varying preferences for the type of podcasts they use to learn English, the student participants showed a clear preference for video podcasts. 49% of respondents indicated that they prefer video podcasts. Meanwhile, 30% of students favored audio podcasts. The remaining 21% stated a preference for enhanced podcasts. These findings suggest that the visual and potentially contextual cues provided by video podcasts are perceived as particularly beneficial for English language learning.

C. Section Three: Attitudes Towards Podcasts

12. Question twelve: Has any of your teachers used podcast as a teaching content before?

Figure 6: Teacher Use of Podcasts

It is clear from Figure 06 that more than half of the participants, 62%, reported that their teachers have used podcasts as teaching content in the classroom. This indicates that podcasts are increasingly being recognized as a valuable instructional tool by teachers. However, 38% of students stated that their teachers have not used podcasts.

13. Question thirteen: If yes, which modules?

All the students who answered "yes" to the previous question indicated that podcasts were used in the oral expression module. Additionally, some students mentioned that podcasts were also integrated into other modules, such as research methodology, literature, didactics, and even French. This suggests that while oral expression is the primary area where podcasts

are integrated, there is also some degree of adoption across a variety of other academic disciplines.

14. Question fourteen: If yes, how would you describe the experience?

Figure 7: Student Experience with Podcasts

The results above show that when asked to describe their experience with podcasts as teaching content, the overwhelming majority of students responded positively. 84% of those who had experienced podcast-based instruction described it as interesting. However, 8% of students found the experience uninteresting, and another 8% described the experience as challenging. This largely positive feedback suggests that students generally find podcasts to be an engaging and appealing medium for learning.

15. Question fifteen: Do you believe using podcasts will help enhance your listening skills?

Table 7: Student Beliefs on Podcasts' Impact on Listening Skills

Options	YES	NO	Total
N°	38	01	39
%	97%	03%	100%

The table reveals that the majority of the participants (97%) responded that they agree with the effectiveness of podcasts in enhancing their listening skill. Only one student, representing 3% of the sample, indicated a negative belief. These findings indicate a very high level of perceived efficacy of podcasts as a tool for developing listening proficiency.

16. Question sixteen: Which language skills do you think podcasts help improve the most?

Figure 8: Podcasts Contribution in Improving Various Skills

The above figure demonstrates that 59% of the respondents believe that listening to podcasts can enhance their listening skill, while 18% use them to improve their vocabulary, and another 13% use them to improve their speaking. Therefore, learners use podcasts to improve skills that they need depending on their level, the remaining 10% reported that they listen to podcasts to enhance their pronunciation.

17. Question seventeen: How effective do you think podcasts are in improving your listening skills?

Table 8: Rating Podcast Effectiveness.

Options	N°	%
Very effective	12	31%
Effective	26	66%
Neutral	01	03%
Ineffective	0	0%
Very ineffective	0	0%
Total	39	100%

The students' perceptions of podcast effectiveness in improving listening skills were very positive. As it is seen in table 08, the majority of students, 66%, find podcasts effective in improving their listening skills. Furthermore, 31% considered them very effective. Only 3% of the participants remained neutral, and no students rated podcasts as ineffective or very ineffective. This indicates a strong belief among the students that podcasts are a valuable tool for enhancing their listening skills.

18. Question eighteen: How comfortable would you be with using podcasts as part of your learning materials?

Table 9: Student Comfort Level with Podcasts as Learning Materials

Options	N°	%
Very comfortable	16	41%
Comfortable	16	41%
Neutral	05	13%
Uncomfortable	02	05%
Very Uncomfortable	0	0%
Total	39	100%

It is clear from the data above that the majority of students feel positively about using podcasts as part of their learning materials. A combined 82% of respondents expressed comfort, with 41% indicating they would be very comfortable and another 41% they would be comfortable. However, 5% remained neutral, expressing neither comfort nor discomfort, while only 2% felt uncomfortable, and no students reported feeling very uncomfortable. This strong indication of comfort among the vast majority of students suggests a positive predisposition towards integrating podcasts into their learning experience.

19. Question nineteen: What do you believe are the benefits of using podcasts for enhancing listening skills?

Figure 9: Students' Perceived Benefits of Using Podcasts for Enhancing Listening Skills

As shown in the figure above, students perceive accessibility 46% as the most significant benefit of using podcasts for enhancing listening skills. Then, Variety of contents was also considered a significant advantage 29%, suggesting that podcasts offer a wide range of materials to cater to diverse student interests and needs. Availability and flexibility were mentioned by 10% of the Students. Finally, exposure to different accents was recognized as a benefit by 15% of the respondents. This data indicates that students highly value the accessibility and variety of content offered by podcasts for improving listening skills. Additionally, students recognize the benefit of exposure to different accents provided by podcasts.

20. Question twenty: What challenges have you faced or do you anticipate facing when using podcasts for learning?

Table 10: The Challenges Encountered While Listening to Podcasts by Students.

Podcasts' Challenges	N°	%
Lack of understanding	13	33%
Technical issues	7	18%
Difficulty in finding relevant content	10	26%
Distraction due to multitasking	9	23%
Total	39	100%

Based on the data provided in the table 10, the primary obstacle faced by students, as indicated by 33% of respondents, is the Lack of understanding. Following that, 26% of participants identified Difficulty in finding relevant content as a significant challenge, while 23 % mentioned the Distraction due to multitasking as a barrier. Lastly, the technical issues were identified as the least common obstacles 18%. This data suggests that the main hurdle for students using podcasts for learning is Lack of understanding. The challenges of finding relevant content and managing distractions also highlight the importance of guidance and strategies for effective podcast integration. While technical issues are the least reported, they still represent a barrier for a notable portion of students.

21. Question twenty one: What do you like most about using podcasts for learning English?

Table 11: Students’ Responses to the Benefits of Using Podcasts for Learning English.

Theme	Example Responses	N°
Improving listening skills	“Improves listening skills”, “Help me to enhance my listening skills”, “Improving our listening skills”	6
Gaining new vocabulary	“Gain new vocabulary”, “Enrich my vocabulary”, “Gaining new vocabulary”	5
Improving pronunciation	“Learning pronunciation”, “Enhancing our pronunciation”, “Enhancing our accents”	4
Exposure to different accents & topics	“Exposure to different accents”, “Different accents and topics”, “Real conversations with various accents”	5
Developing all four skills	“Enhancing my four skills”, “Improve our skills especially listening and speaking”	3
Accessibility & flexibility	“Anytime and anywhere”, “During free time like walking or travelling”, “Easy and accessible”	5
Enjoyable learning experience	“It is enjoyable”, “It is a funny way to learn English”, “More enjoyable”	4
Cost-effective and rich in content	“Costing less money”, “Very useful tool to learn English because it is so rich by information”	2

When asked what they liked most about using podcasts to learn English, 22 students shared a variety of thoughts, many of which overlapped in meaning.

One of the most common responses was related to listening skills six (06) students specifically said that podcasts helped them improve how they understand spoken English. Gaining new vocabulary followed closely, with five (05) students expressing that podcasts helped them gain new words and phrases in context. Another five (05) students appreciated being exposed to a variety of accents and topics, which they felt made the content more engaging and closer to real-life use of English. In a similar pattern, five (05)

students said they liked the flexibility and accessibility of podcasts mentioning how convenient it is to listen while doing other things, such as walking or during breaks.

Some students also pointed out how podcasts helped with pronunciation four (04) of them mentioned that hearing native speakers improved the way they speak. Enjoyment was another notable theme, mentioned by four (04) students who described podcasts as more fun and relaxing than traditional classroom methods. Three participants said that podcasts helped them improve all four language skills (listening, speaking, reading, and writing). Finally, two (02) students brought up the fact that podcasts are not only helpful but also affordable and packed with useful information.

Taking all of this into account, it's clear that students see podcasts as a practical, flexible, and effective way to learn English. Many of them believe that podcasts help them to improve their four skills especially listening. Their responses suggest that podcasts are not just a casual learning tool, they're something students genuinely enjoy and find useful in their everyday learning routines. With the right content and support, podcasts have the potential to play a much more central role in the EFL classroom.

22. Question twenty two: Would you recommend using podcasts as a tool for improving listening skills in EFL classes?

Figure 10: Students' Recommendation of Podcasts as a Teaching Tool

It can be seen from figure 10 that students are positively inclined towards the use of podcasts for improving listening skills in the EFL classroom, with 30 students expressing a

positive stance. A smaller number of students, specifically eight (08), indicated uncertainty, while only one (01) student demonstrated a negative disposition. The vastly positive response demonstrates that the majority of the students consider podcasts an effective method of improving their listening skills in an EFL environment.

23. Question twenty three: What improvements or changes would you suggest to make podcasts more effective for language learning?

Table 12: : Students’ Suggestions for Improving the Effectiveness of Podcasts in Language Learning.

Theme	Example Responses	N°
Shorter and more focused content	“It must be shorter and the content should be specific”; “Podcast should be less than 30 minutes”; “Make the content concise”	6
Topic relevance and variety	“Provide more topics and it should be suitable to all ages”; “Select interesting topics based on learners’ needs”	5
Clarity and speech pace	“Use clear, slow speech”; “Make the podcast slow”; “Teachers should use clear tone and voice”	4
Use of transcripts / subtitles	“Use subtitles, transcript”; “Provide transcript for better understanding”	4
Simple and understandable language	“Use simple language so everyone can understand”; “Make the content more accessible linguistically”	4
Guidance and recommendations	“We need suggestions from teachers”; “Podcast creators should provide content summaries in the description box”	3
Better speakers and delivery	“Bring good speakers”; “Use good quality voice and content delivery”	3

In response to the open-ended question about improving podcasts for language learning, students offered a range of suggestions, which were grouped into key themes to avoid repetition. A notable theme was the length and focus of content, as six (06) students suggested that podcasts should be shortened, focused, and preferably not longer than 30 minutes. They also emphasized the need to make content more focused and directly relevant to learning objectives.

Another significant area highlighted by five (05) students was the selection of topics. They suggested incorporating varied topics, more engaging and suitable for students of all ages. Some students believed that the effectiveness of podcasts could be significantly improved if the topics matched students' interests and needs.

Clarity of speech was another area of concern. Four (04) students asked for slower and clearer audio delivery, as fast or unclear speech could affect comprehension. This ties in closely with the use of transcripts or subtitles, which four (04) students specifically requested to help with following along and understanding the spoken content more effectively.

In addition, four students emphasized the need for simple and accessible language, pointing out that complex vocabulary or sentence structures may hinder understanding. Three additional students suggested teachers should assist learners in selecting useful podcast content and creators offer brief summaries or points to help listeners decide if an episode is worth their time.

Finally, three students suggested the quality of delivery in podcasts to be improved by using professional or skilled speakers to improve engagement and clarity.

Overall, students reported that they would like podcasts to be simple, clear, and simple to follow. They prefer shorter episodes and interesting, related subjects, and value clear speech, simple vocabulary, and some extra help such as transcripts or teacher recommendations. Their feedback shows that they're not just looking for content but also they want podcasts to be helpful, interesting, and at their level. With some considerate changes, podcasts could be a significantly better resource and enjoyable part of their language learning experience.

2.5.2 Teachers' Questionnaire

For practicality reasons and for teachers' convenience, the teachers' questionnaire, which was divided into four sections, was created and administered using Google Forms, with a link sent directly via email to 18 EFL teachers within the English Department at Relizane University. Of these, 10 teachers responded and constitute the sample for this research. The analysis of this questionnaire will proceed as follows:

A. Section One: Background Information

1. Question One: What is your gender?

Table 13: Teachers' Gender Distribution

Options	Male	Female
N°	4	6
%	40%	60%

According to the table above, the gender distribution of the teacher participants reveals a higher proportion of female teachers. 60% of the respondents were female, while 40% were male. This indicates a slightly greater representation of female educators within the sample group.

2. Question Two: Teachers' Age

Figure 11: Teachers' Age Distribution

The age profile of the respondents among the teachers shows that the largest proportion 50% falls within the 29-33 age range. Following this, 20% of the teachers are in the +45 age group. The remaining respondents are distributed across the younger and middle age ranges, with 10% being 23-28 years old, 10% being 34-39 years old, and another 10% being 40-45 years old. This indicates a relatively young to middle-aged teaching sample, with a notable presence of more experienced educators as well.

3. Question Three: How many years of teaching experience do you have?

Figure 12: Teachers' Teaching Experience

In this question, participants were asked about their years of teaching experience. The teaching experience among the teacher respondents is varied. 40% of the teachers reported less than 5 years of experience. 30% had 5 to 10 years of experience, and another 30% had over 10 years of experience. This distribution suggests a mix of early-career, mid-career, and experienced educators within the sample.

B. Section Two: General Use of Podcasts

4. Question Four: Do you listen to podcasts?

Table 14: Teachers' Podcast Listening Habits

Options	Yes	No	Total
N°	8	2	10
%	80%	20%	100%

As illustrated in the table above, the majority of the respondents (80%, representing 8 out of 10 teachers) indicated that they do listen to podcasts. A smaller proportion (20%, representing 2 out of 10 teachers) reported that they do not listen to podcasts. This suggests a generally high level of familiarity with the medium among the teachers.

5. Question Five: Have you ever used podcasts as a teaching tool in your EFL classes?

Figure 13: Teachers' Use of Podcasts in EFL Teaching

It is clear from the data above that a significant majority of the teachers who took part in this survey have experience using podcasts as a teaching tool in their EFL classes. 70% of the participants reported having used podcasts as a teaching medium in the EFL classroom, and

30% said they had not. This reflects a relatively high level of use of podcasts as an educational tool by the EFL teachers included in this survey.

6. Question Six: If yes, which module do you use podcasts in?

When asked teachers which module they use podcasts in, all 70% of the teachers who responded 'yes' in the previous question (Have you ever used podcasts as a teaching tool in your EFL classes?), they reported using them in the oral expression module. This indicates a strong consensus among the teachers who utilize podcasts, with oral expression being the primary context for their implementation.

7. Question Seven: How often do you use podcasts in your teaching?

Table 15: Teachers’ Frequency of Podcast Use in EFL Teaching

Options	Never	Rarely	Occasionally	Frequently	Always	Total
N°	3	1	6	0	0	10
%	30%	10%	60%	00%	00%	100%

In this question, the findings indicate varying degrees of the frequency with which teachers utilize podcasts in instruction. 60%, of the respondents said that they use podcasts occasionally. Conversely, 30% mentioned that they never used podcasts . 10% of them use podcasts rarely. Strikingly, no teachers said that they use podcasts often or always for instruction. This would mean that while there are instructors who are utilizing podcasts during class, it is not yet a regular practice with the majority of instructors.

8. Question Eight: What types of podcasts do you use or recommend for EFL teaching?

Figure 14: Teacher Preferences in Podcast Types for EFL Instruction

As it can be seen in the figure above, the teachers' preferences for podcast types used or recommended for EFL teaching vary. Video podcasts emerge as the most favored format, selected by 60% of respondents, while 30% use or recommend audio podcasts. Only 10% indicated using or recommending enhanced podcasts. This suggests that video podcasts are the most popular format among EFL teachers, possibly due to the added visual component.

C. Section Three: Attitudes Towards Podcasts

9. Question Nine: Do you believe podcasts are effective in enhancing students' listening skills?

Table 16: Teachers' Perceptions of Podcast Effectiveness for Listening Skills

Options	Yes	No	Not Sure	Total
N°	9	0	1	10
%	90%	00%	10%	100%

In this question, the results show that the majority of the participants believe that podcasts can enhance students' listening skills. 90% of the teachers expressed a positive stance, aligning with their belief about the effectiveness of podcasts towards enhancing listening

skills, while a small minority 10% of the teachers, indicated uncertainty, while zero percent (0%) demonstrated a negative disposition. This suggests a high level of agreement between the participants regarding the efficacy of podcasts as a tool for improving students' listening skills, with no disagreement from any of the teachers.

10. Question Ten: How comfortable are you with integrating podcasts into your teaching materials?

Figure 15: Teachers' Comfort Levels with Podcast Integration

From the responses shown in the figure above, the data indicates that teachers generally feel comfortable with using podcasts in their teaching materials. 60% of the respondents reported feeling comfortable, and 30% felt very comfortable. 10% of the teachers expressed a neutral in their attitude, and no teachers reported any level of discomfort. This strong positive sentiment suggests that the teacher sample is largely receptive to and confident in the potential of using podcasts as a pedagogical tool.

11. Question Eleven: What do you perceive as the main benefits of using podcasts in EFL teaching?

Table 17: Teachers' Ranked Benefits of Podcasts in EFL Instruction

Podcasts' Benefits	N°	%
Improved listening skills	5	50%
Exposure to authentic language	4	40%
Increased student engagement	1	10%
Flexibility in learning	0	00%
Total	10	100%

The results of this question show that EFL teachers list three primary benefits of podcast use, with improved listening skill as the dominant benefit (50% of all answers). The second most mentioned benefit is exposure to authentic language (40%). A smaller but significant minority of participants (10%) emphasize increased student engagement. This indicates that teachers primarily value podcasts for their direct impact on listening comprehension and for providing learners with exposure to real-world language use, with student engagement also being recognized.

12. Question Twelve: What challenges have you faced when using podcasts in your teaching?

Figure 16: Teachers' Challenges in Podcast Implementation

The purpose of this question is to explore the different challenges encountered by EFL teachers when using podcasts in their teaching. The most cited challenge among teachers was the lack of technical resources (57.14%). Difficulty in finding relevant content was also stated as a challenge by 14.28% of the respondents. Furthermore, 28.57% of the participants cited difficulty due to limited class time. This data highlights that practical constraints, particularly the availability of necessary technology, represent the most substantial barrier for teachers who would like to integrate podcasts into their EFL lessons. The challenges of content selection and time constraints also underscore the need for readily accessible, relevant materials and efficient pedagogical strategies for podcast implementation.

D. Section Four : Support, Training, and Recommendations

13. Question Thirteen: Do you feel adequately trained to use podcasts as a teaching tool?

Figure 17: Teacher Training for Podcast Use

The results above reveal that teachers' perceptions about their training to use podcasts as a teaching resource are divided. 40% of the sample felt adequately trained. However, 30% said that they do not feel adequately trained, and another 30% said that they feel only 'somewhat' trained. It can thus be a requirement for extra support and learning in the educational use of podcasts.

14. Question Fourteen: What support or resources would help you use podcasts more effectively in your teaching?

Table 18: Support and Resources for Podcast Use

Options	N°	%
Training workshops	4	40%
Access to curated podcast lists	1	10%
Technical support	5	50%
Total	10	100%

It is obvious from the table above that teachers indicated the necessity of various types of support and resources in order to provide them with proper utilization of podcasts within the classroom. Technical support was found to be the most vital resource, mentioned by 50% of the sample. Training workshops were also considered crucial by 40% of the teachers. A smaller percentage, 10% stated that access to curated podcast lists would be useful. The data reveals that EFL teachers believe technical support is the most crucial resource for more effective podcast integration in their teaching. Following closely is the need for training workshops to guide their pedagogical approaches. Additionally, access to curated podcast lists is seen as a helpful resource for content selection.

15. Question Fifteen: Would you recommend using podcasts as a teaching tool for improving listening skills in EFL classes?

Figure 18: Teachers' Recommendation of Podcasts as a Teaching Tool

In response to this question, the participants came to a consensus unanimously. All (100%) of the teachers stated that they would suggest using podcasts as a teaching material for improving listening skills in EFL classes. This indicates strong support from EFL teachers for the use of podcasts in enhancing students' listening skill.

16. Question Sixteen: What improvement or suggestions do you have for making podcasts more effective in EFL teaching? Feel free to include specific examples or ideas.

Table 19: Teachers’ Suggestions for Making Podcasts More Effective in EFL Teaching

N°	Teacher Suggestions
1	Teachers should emphasize the importance of authentic language through podcasts. Administration should provide proper materials like good-quality speakers and projectors to support podcast use in the classroom.
2	Begin with brainstorming before playing the podcast. Give students a task while listening, and follow up with reflection and discussion. Link back to target expressions to reinforce the lesson objective.
3	Use podcasts that feature authentic language, include famous figures (e.g., singers, influencers), and cover interesting topics for students such as sports, fashion, cooking, and dancing.
4	Ensure the availability of proper technical equipment and select appropriate types of podcasts for integration into oral sessions.
5	Carefully select podcast content that captures the learners’ attention.
6	Encourage students to participate in the creation of their own podcasts.
7	Select the most appropriate podcasts and teaching materials to use in class.

It must be noted that out of 10 teachers who were emailed this open-ended question, only seven (07) responded. However, the responses that were received were rich in insight and had practical suggestions of how podcasts could be integrated more effectively into the EFL classroom. Their suggestions are summarized in table 19 above.

Some teachers stressed the necessity of authentic content. They think that podcasts must have real-life language, known characters like singers or influencers, and subjects that

students really like—such as sports, fashion, or cooking. This indicates that teachers know how relevant, interesting content can enhance student motivation and engagement.

A further region of similarity was a call for more productive lesson planning in the use of podcasts. One teacher, for example, proposed using a brainstorming activity as a starting point, assigning an activity for students to do during listening, and ending with reflection and class discussion. Step by step in such a manner benefits not just listening, but also encourages critical thinking and reinforces learning objectives.

Some of the teachers reported some technical problems that can risk the use of podcasts in a classroom. They highlighted the need to have good-quality speakers, projectors, and administrative support to ensure podcasts can be effectively utilized in the classroom environment.

One option that was highly recommended was allowing the students to create their own podcasts. This is an active learning activity that could promote active learning, creativity, and deeper language engagement.

The selection of appropriate content was also repeatedly mentioned. Teachers advised that podcasts should be well curated, age-appropriate, and aligned with lesson objectives, ensuring that the material is both interesting and pedagogically effective.

Overall, the teacher responses suggest that they see great potential in the application of podcasts as a teaching tool for English instruction specifically to improve listening and make classroom experience more engaging. Their suggestions highlight the importance of using authentic, relevant content, planning lessons effectively, and ensuring that both teachers and students have the right resources and support.

2.6 Discussion of the findings

This study involved thirty nine (39) third year LMD students from the Department of English at Relizane University, aiming to explore their attitudes toward podcasts as instructional material for enhancing listening skills. Additionally, ten (10) other EFL teachers from the same department also took part in the study, so as to contribute more profoundly to the pedagogical aspect of podcasts. The results of both questionnaires yielded significant

results about attitudes, perceptions, habits, and preferences towards podcast use for the EFL learning.

2.6.1 Students' Questionnaire Discussion

The results found in this research work can be categorized into three main parts: the students' familiarity with the use of podcasts, their attitudes toward podcasts in the educational field, and their future hopes concerning the integration of podcasts in educational settings.

The present study focused on a group of thirty nine (39) third-year LMD students from the Department of English in Relizane University and their attitudes towards podcasts as an instructional material for listening. The sample consisted of nine males and thirty females, aged twenty to twenty-two years old.

The analysis of the students' questionnaire indicated that the vast majority (95%) of them listened to podcasts, so there is a high level of familiarity and engagement with this medium. One of the key findings was that 100% of students access podcasts via smartphones. Every single respondent uses their smartphone, reflecting the importance of mobile technology in their learning habits. While not all students listen frequently, a good number stated they use podcasts occasionally, indicating growing interest and exposure.

The duration of podcast listening sessions varied, with 43% spending more than 30 minutes per session, indicating sustained engagement. English dominates their listening choices (76%), reinforcing its role as a key tool for EFL learning. Students showed a preference for interview (35%) and solo formats (23%), with the self-improvement genre being the clear favorite (46%). These findings suggest that students are already comfortable with the use of podcasts as an educational and entertaining platform.

When we asked students about their podcast routines, some fascinating patterns emerged. 86% admitted they specifically use podcasts to learn English. Students also shared their preferences when it came to podcast types. Audio podcasts were clearly favored over video or enhanced formats. This may be because audio podcasts are easier to access and less demanding in terms of focus and data use.

Then, 62% reported their teachers had used podcasts; 38% had never integrated them in class. Those who had were overwhelmingly positive 84% described the experience as interesting, and all students who said that their teachers used podcasts answered that they integrate them in oral expression module.

Students had generally positive attitudes toward podcasting as a learning tool. 97% believed that podcasts enhance their listening skills, many saw podcasts as an effective way to expand their vocabulary and practice pronunciation, with 66% finding podcasts effective and 31% very effective. The majority 82% felt comfortable using them for study.

Students also highlighted the accessibility of podcasts. 46% said they liked being able to listen during breaks, while walking, or even traveling, appreciating how accessible they are, the variety of content available (29%), and exposure to different accents (15%). However, challenges such as lack of understanding (33%) and difficulty in finding suitable content (26%) were experienced, indicating areas for improvement.

The positive experiences reported by 84% of students who had used podcasts in class further validate their effectiveness as an instructional tool. Students expressed strong support for integrating podcasts into EFL classrooms, with 77% recommending their use. Their suggestions for improvement focused on shorter, more focused content, clearer speech, and the inclusion of transcripts. They also emphasized the need for topic relevance and variety, and simpler language.

These insights highlight a desire for podcasts that are pedagogically effective, engaging, and tailored to their learning needs. The findings suggest that with proper adjustments such as better structured content and teacher guidance podcasts could become a more central component of EFL instruction.

2.6.2 Teachers' Questionnaire Discussion

Ten EFL teachers, six female (60%) and four male (40%), from Relizane University participated in this study to share their attitudes, views and experiences with podcast use in the classroom, representing a range of age groups and experience levels. Half of the respondents (50%) fell within the 29–33 age, while others were distributed across younger (23–28: 10%) and more experienced (40–45: 10%); (+45: 20%).

In terms of professional experience, 40% with less than five years' experience, 30% with 5–10 years, and 30% with over ten years in the field. Within this diverse group, 80% reported personal podcast usage, indicating substantial baseline familiarity with the medium. Notably, 70% had incorporated podcasts into their classroom teaching, primarily in oral expression modules. This discrepancy suggests that despite recognizing podcasts' value, most teachers were having trouble turning private consumption into classroom use. The preferred type was clearly video podcasts (60%), likely due to their multimodal benefits for language learners, though audio (30%) and enhanced podcasts (10%) also had their proponents among the teaching staff.

Teachers showed almost universal confidence in the pedagogical usefulness of podcasts, with 90% confirming their utility for the improvement of listening skills. Specifically, they highlighted three benefits: improved listening comprehension (50%), exposure to authentic language use (40%), and increased student engagement (10%). However, 10% remained uncertain about their impact, suggesting the need for more evidence-based implementation strategies. Comfort levels with integration were uniformly high 90% combined "comfortable" and "very comfortable" responses. The most frequently cited challenge was inadequate technical resources (57.14%), while time constraints (28.57%) were more frequently cited by instructors with heavier teaching loads. Some teachers (14.28%) found it difficult to locate appropriate content matching their students' proficiency levels and course objectives.

When asked about necessary support systems, teachers identified three critical requirements: improved technical infrastructure (50%), training workshops (40%), and access to curated podcasts lists (10%). Despite these challenges, 100% of participating teachers supported the expanded use of podcast in EFL instruction, proposing several thoughtful recommendations for improvement. These included selecting clear, age appropriate content, ensuring short duration "less than 30 minutes", and incorporating pre-listening and post-listening activities to reinforce learning. They also emphasized the need for institutional support, such as providing audio-visual tools and access to curated podcast libraries.

From the data, it is evident that teachers are willing to use podcasts more often. With better support and targeted training, teachers could use podcasts as an interactive and flexible tool for enhancing listening skills.

2.6.3. Discussion of the Overall Findings

This study explored the attitudes of both EFL teachers and third-year students at Relizane University toward the use of podcasts as instructional material for enhancing listening skills. The findings demonstrated that students are not only familiar with podcasts but also positively inclined towards their integration into language learning. These findings strongly align with the literature reviewed in Chapter One, which emphasized podcasts as engaging, flexible, and authentic tools for language acquisition (Rosell-Aguilar, 2007; Gromik, 2008; Evans, 2008). Consistent with studies by (Rahman et al, 2018; Wardana, 2024; Djellouli & Elalia, 2023), the results showed that students believe podcasts help develop essential listening competencies, including comprehension, vocabulary, pronunciation, and exposure to various English accents. Additionally, the majority of students preferred audio podcasts and expressed appreciation for their accessibility via smartphones, echoing literature emphasizing the mobility and convenience of podcasting (Lauer, 2018; Read, 2007).

From the teachers' perspective, the data revealed a generally supportive stance toward integrating podcasts into EFL instruction, particularly in oral expression modules. This mirrors the theoretical discussion in Chapter One, where teachers were shown to recognize the pedagogical benefits of podcasts, especially in offering authentic listening experiences and increasing learner engagement (Moussaoui, 2019; Mohammed & Khadawardi, 2024). However, some challenges were also acknowledged. These included technical resources (57.14%) and time constraints (28.57%) as major barriers to integration, echoing concerns raised by Suseno (2024). These obstacles highlight the need for institutional support, such as curated podcast libraries and teacher training, to maximize the medium's potential.

Both participants offered suggestions and recommendations for improvement, with students requesting shorter episodes, transcripts, and simpler language, while teachers emphasized the need for structured pre- and post-listening activities. These suggestions align with pedagogical strategies proposed by Rost (2011) and Ur (1989), reinforcing the importance of scaffolding and context in listening instruction.

In conclusion, results derived from the two questionnaires show that teachers and students generally view podcasts positively towards enhancing listening skills in the EFL environment. The alignment between theory and data provides strong evidence supporting the pedagogical integration of podcasts in EFL contexts.

2.7 Recommendations

In the light of our findings, we would like to present some recommendations that may be beneficial for the integration of podcasts into EFL instruction at Relizane University. The following recommendations must be taken into consideration:

- Teachers need special training concerning the use of ICT tools, particularly podcasts.
- Laboratories should be provided for EFL students to practice and improve their listening skills using authentic audio materials.
- Students should be encouraged to use podcasts outside the classroom as supplementary learning material to develop their listening and speaking abilities.
- Teachers should stay updated with technological advancements and align their teaching strategies with modern ICT tools such as podcasts.
- Curriculum designers should be aware of the involvement of technology in the educational field and integrate ICT tools, including podcasts, into language learning syllabi to meet current and future educational needs.
- Teachers should actively incorporate podcasts into their lessons to enrich classroom learning with real-world content and enhance students' exposure to authentic language use.
- Teachers who use podcasts in their teaching should focus on content that meets learners' needs, utilize native speaker audio, and select engaging topics.

- The English department of Relizane University should produce original podcasts that learners can download and use to their benefit. These podcasts could be shared with other universities to expand their accessibility and influence.

2.8 Limitations

In any research study, researchers face obstacles and challenges while investigating and collecting valid data. This dissertation has also some limitations that can be stated as follows:

- One of the most significant limitations of this study was the distribution and collection of the teachers' questionnaire. Initially the questionnaire was intended to be sent exclusively to teachers specializing in oral expression module. However, a significant number of these targeted teachers did not respond to our email and did not complete the questionnaire. This lack of participation reduced the expected sample size and may have limited the representativeness of the collected data.
- Some students were not very responsible in their answers or answering randomly without deep responsible thinking, some questions were left unanswered, which obstructed the process of analysis.
- The study's short duration and the students' varying proficiency levels and awareness of podcasts may have contributed to potential limitations and unstable outcomes.
- We faced difficulties in finding sources in the library. Thus, we depended on E-books and articles to collect data and have access to previous studies.

Conclusion

This chapter dealt with the practical part of this study. It covered a description of the research settings and population and showed the data gathered from the analysis of the research instruments (students' questionnaire and teachers' questionnaire). It also revealed the discussion of the findings collected from the research tools. To sum up, the findings from both research instruments employed here verify that podcasts are perceived as a useful resource for listening development in language learning by EFL learners and teachers.

Findings confirm that students have a positive perception of learning through podcast and that teachers perceive the pedagogical benefits of podcasting despite challenges. The results of this study highlight the promise of podcasts for effective EFL instruction, especially in enhancing listening comprehension.

General Conclusion

General Conclusion

This research investigated EFL teachers' and students' attitudes towards using podcasts to improve the listening skill. It aimed at finding out whether or not the teachers and students had positive attitudes towards using podcasts to enhance students' listening skills. That is, determining if the teachers and students found podcasts as an effective teaching resource to be implemented in the classroom in order to develop the learners listening abilities.

This research was divided into two chapters, the theoretical part and the field work. The theoretical part consists of two sections in which the study was about the two variables of the topic. The first section provides an overview of podcast including definition, features, benefits, and challenges in implementation. Special attention is given to podcasts in the EFL context. The section further includes podcasts as a language learning material, effectiveness of podcasts for listening skills, and general attitudes toward podcasts. The second section, however, focuses on the second variable, which is listening comprehension. It begins by defining listening skills, emphasizing the importance of listening skills, it provides the different stages, types, and then moving to listening comprehension, following it by approaches, difficulties that EFL learners may face during listening, and finishing by the importance of listening comprehension in EFL teaching and learning. The second chapter dealt with the methodology used in this investigation. The chapter started by mentioning the research design, settings, and fieldwork access, followed by a representation of the participants and the data collection instruments used. To answer the research questions, the researchers adopted a qualitative approach for collecting and analyzing the data. A questionnaire was administered to thirty-nine (39) third-year LMD students from the department of English at Relizane University. In addition, to further enhance the study results, the researchers also administered a Google Forms questionnaire to ten (10) EFL teachers. The second chapter dealt also with interpreting the data gathered from both the students' and teachers' questionnaires, followed by a discussion of the results, and concludes with recommendations and limitations.

The data gathered from the students' questionnaires demonstrate a largely positive attitude towards using podcasts to enhance their listening skills. The majority of students

expressed interest in utilizing podcasts for learning and reported that they found them effective in improving not only their listening comprehension but also related skills like vocabulary acquisition and pronunciation. Students also valued the flexibility and accessibility of podcasts, as well as the exposure they provided to real, everyday English. Furthermore, they expressed the belief that integrating podcasts into EFL classrooms as educational material could significantly improve their listening abilities.

The findings from the teachers' questionnaires reveal a generally positive perception and attitude towards the potential of podcasts as an instructional material in EFL settings. Teachers recognized the value of podcasts, particularly in providing authentic listening input and enriching oral expression classes. They expressed a willingness and intention to incorporate podcasts more regularly into their teaching practices, indicating a positive disposition towards their use for language instruction. However, this positive outlook was often tempered by practical challenges such as technical issues and a perceived lack of necessary resources, which currently limit their implementation. Teachers emphasized that their effective use of podcasts hinges on their own familiarity with the medium, adequate support and training, and the careful selection of relevant, goal oriented content. Through the review of the students' and teachers' questionnaires, this study suggests a generally positive disposition towards the use of podcasts as an instructional material for enhancing listening skills in the EFL context.

In conclusion, this study indicates that podcasts play an important role in developing EFL learners' listening skills and are a reliable and relevant tool for listening practice and knowledge enrichment. Therefore, teachers should integrate and rely on them to help students develop not only their listening skills but also their other language skills.

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Appendices

Appendix one: Students' Questionnaire

Dear Students,

This investigation aims to explore “EFL Teachers’ and Students' Attitudes towards Podcasts as Instructional Material to Enhance Students' Listening Skills”. This study is conducted by Belharret Oussama and Amazouz Walid, under the supervision of Ms. Amina Aissa Assia as part of the requirements to get a Master’s in Language and communication.

The participation in this study involves answering a set of questions where there is no right or wrong answers.

The anonymity and confidentiality of your identity and your answers will be kept throughout the process of data collection, data analysis and data reporting. Additionally, the collected data will be used for the sole purposes of this study. Finally, there are no known risks to participating in this study.

Your participation is fully voluntary and you can withdraw at any moment.

Please, tick (✓) the appropriate answer or provide your response where required.

A. Background Information

1. Gender: Male Female

2. Age :

B. General Consumption of Podcasts

3. Do you listen to podcasts? If no, please skip to part C.

Yes No

4. How often do you listen to podcasts?

Never Rarely Occasionally Frequently Always

5. Which device do you mostly use to access podcasts?

Smartphone

Laptop

Tablet

Other (please specify):

6. On average, how much time do you spend listening to podcasts per session?

More than 30 minutes

15 to 30 minutes

Less than 15 minutes

7. In what language(s) are the podcasts you listen to? (Select all the ones that apply ranking them with 1 being the common one)

Arabic

English

French

Other:

8. Which podcast format do you enjoy the most? (Select as many that apply ranking them with 1 being the most listened to)

Interview Podcasts

Educational & How-To Podcasts

Solo (Monologue) Podcasts

News & Current Events

Conversational (Co-hosted) Podcasts

Panel Discussions

Narrative Storytelling (Fiction)

Documentary-Style Podcasts

Narrative Storytelling (Nonfiction)

9. Which podcast format do you enjoy the most? (Select as many as apply and rank them starting with 1 being the most listened to)

True Crime

Comedy

Business & Finance

Health & Wellness

Technology

Pop Culture & Entertainment

Science & Nature

History

Self-Improvement & Productivity

Hobbies & Niche Interests

10. Do you listen to podcasts to learn English?

Yes

No

11. Which type of podcast do you prefer for learning English? (If many apply, rank them starting with 1)

- Audio podcasts (voice recordings, interviews, discussions)
- Video podcasts (videos with visuals and subtitles)
- Enhanced podcasts (audio with images, texts, and interactive elements)

C. Attitudes Towards Podcasts

12. Has any of your teachers used podcast as a teaching content before?

- Yes No

13. If yes, which modules?

.....

14. If yes, how would you describe the experience?

- Interesting uninteresting challenging

Other:

15. Do you believe using podcasts will help enhance your listening skills?

- Yes. No

16. Which language skills do you think podcasts help improve the most? (rank them starting with 1)

- Listening Speaking Pronunciation Vocabulary

17. How effective do you think podcasts are in improving your listening skills?

- Very effective
- Effective
- Neutral
- Ineffective
- Very ineffective

18. How comfortable would you be with using podcasts as part of your learning materials?

- Very comfortable
- Comfortable
- Neutral

- Uncomfortable
- Very Uncomfortable

19. What do you believe are the benefits of using podcasts for enhancing listening skills?

(Select all that apply)

- Accessibility (can listen anytime, anywhere)
- Variety of contents
- Availability and flexibility
- Exposure to different accents

Other (please specify).....
.....

20. What challenges have you faced or do you anticipate facing when using podcasts for learning? (Select all that apply)

- Lack of understanding
- Technical issues
- Difficulty in finding relevant content
- Distraction due to multitasking

Other (please specify)
.....

21. What do you like most about using podcasts for learning English?

.....
.....

22. Would you recommend using podcasts as a tool for improving listening skills in EFL classes?

- Yes No Not sure

23. What improvements or changes would you suggest to make podcasts more effective for language learning?

.....

.....
.....

Dear Students,

This investigation aims to explore "EFL Teachers' and Students' Attitudes Towards Podcasts as Instructional Material to Enhance Students' Listening Skills". This study is conducted by Amazzouz Walid and Belharet Oussama, under the supervision of Ms. Amina Aissa Assia as part of the requirements to get a Master's in Language and communication.

The participation in this study involves answering a set of questions where there is no right or wrong answers.

The anonymity and confidentiality of your identity and your answers will be kept throughout the process of data collection, data analysis and data reporting. Additionally, the collected data will be used for the sole purposes of this study. Finally, there are no known risks to participating in this study.

Your participation is fully voluntary and you can withdraw at any moment.

Please, tick (✓) the appropriate answer or provide your response where required.

A. Background Information

1. Gender: Male Female

2. Age : 20.

B. General Consumption of Podcasts

3. Do you listen to podcasts? If no, please skip to part C.

Yes No

4. How often do you listen to podcasts?

Never Rarely Occasionally Frequently Always

5. Which device do you mostly use to access podcasts?

Smartphone Laptop Tablet

Other (please specify):

6. On average, how much time do you spend listening to podcasts per session?

More than 30 minutes 15 to 30 minutes. Less than 15 minutes

7. In what language(s) are the podcasts you listen to? (Select all the ones that apply ranking them with 1 being the common one)

Arabic English French

Other:

8. Which podcast format do you enjoy the most? (Select as many that apply ranking them with 1 being the most listened to)

- | | |
|--|--|
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Interview Podcasts | <input type="checkbox"/> Educational & How-To Podcasts |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Solo (Monologue) Podcasts | <input type="checkbox"/> News & Current Events |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Conversational (Co-hosted) Podcasts | <input type="checkbox"/> Panel Discussions |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Narrative Storytelling (Fiction) | <input type="checkbox"/> Documentary-Style Podcasts |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Narrative Storytelling (Nonfiction) | |

9. Which podcast format do you enjoy the most? (Select as many as apply and rank them starting with 1 being the most listened to)

- | | | |
|---|---|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> True Crime | <input type="checkbox"/> Comedy | <input type="checkbox"/> Business & Finance |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Health & Wellness | <input type="checkbox"/> Technology | <input type="checkbox"/> History |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Science & Nature | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Self-Improvement & Productivity | <input type="checkbox"/> Pop Culture & Entertainment |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Hobbies & Niche Interests | | |

10. Do you listen to podcasts to learn English? Yes No

11. Which type of podcast do you prefer for learning English? (If many apply, rank them starting with 1)

- Audio podcasts (voice recordings, interviews, discussions)
- Video podcasts (videos with visuals and subtitles)
- Enhanced podcasts (audio with images, texts, and interactive elements)

C. Attitudes Towards Podcasts

12. Has any of your teachers used podcast as a teaching content before? Yes No

13. If yes, which modules?

14. If yes, how would you describe the experience?

- Interesting uninteresting challenging

Other:.....

15. Do you believe using podcasts will help enhance your listening skills? Yes. No

16. Which language skills do you think podcasts help improve the most? (rank them starting with 1)

- 1 Listening 3 Speaking 2 Pronunciation 4 Vocabulary

17. How effective do you think podcasts are in improving your listening skills?

- Very effective Effective Neutral Ineffective Very ineffective

18. How comfortable would you be with using podcasts as part of your learning materials?

- Very comfortable Comfortable Neutral Uncomfortable Very Uncomfortable

19. What do you believe are the benefits of using podcasts for enhancing listening skills? (Select all that apply)

- Accessibility (can listen anytime, anywhere)
- Variety of contents
- Availability and flexibility
- Exposure to different accents
- Other (please specify).....

20. What challenges have you faced or do you anticipate facing when using podcasts for learning? (Select all that apply)

- Lack of understanding
- Technical issues
- Difficulty in finding relevant content
- Distraction due to multitasking
- Other (please specify)

21. What do you like most about using podcasts for learning English?

I can learn early while multitasking and the accessibility

22. Would you recommend using podcasts as a tool for improving listening skills in EFL classes?

- Yes No Not sure

23. What improvements or changes would you suggest to make podcasts more effective for language learning?

.....

Appendix Two: Teachers' Questionnaire

Dear Teacher,

You are kindly requested to answer this questionnaire that will be used to accomplish this research about “EFL Teachers’ and Students' Attitudes Towards Podcasts as Instructional Material to Enhance Students' Listening Skills” at the department of English, University of Relizane. This study is conducted by Belharret Oussama and Amazouz Walid , under the supervision of Ms. Amina Aissa Assia as part of the requirements to get a Master’s in Language and communication.

The participation in this study involves answering a set of questions where there is no right or wrong answers.

Your opinions are highly valuable and significant for this research. Rest assured that your answers will be kept strictly confidential. Your participation is greatly appreciated.

Please, tick (√) the appropriate answer or provide your response where required.

A. Background Information

1. What is your gender?

- Male
- Female

2. Age:

23-28 29-33 34-39 40-45 +45

3. How many years of teaching experience do you have?

Less than 5 years 5 to 10 years More than 10 years

B. General Use of Podcasts

4. Do you listen to podcasts?

Yes No

5. Have you ever used podcasts as a teaching tool in your EFL classes?

Yes

No

6. If yes, which module do you use podcasts in?

.....

7. How often do you use podcasts in your teaching?

- Never
- Rarely
- Occasionally
- Frequently
- Always

8. What types of podcasts do you use or recommend for EFL teaching? (Select all that apply)

- Audio podcasts (voice recordings, interviews, discussions)
- Video podcasts (videos with visuals and subtitles)
- Enhanced podcasts (audio with images, texts, and interactive elements)

Other (please specify):

.....

C. Attitudes Towards Podcasts

9. Do you believe podcasts are effective in enhancing students' listening skills?

Yes

No

Not sure

10. How comfortable are you with integrating podcasts into your teaching materials?

- Very comfortable
- Comfortable
- Neutral
- Uncomfortable
- Very uncomfortable

11. What do you perceive as the main benefits of using podcasts in EFL teaching?

(Select all that apply)

- Improved listening skills
- Exposure to authentic language
- Increased student engagement
- Flexibility in learning

- Other (please specify):

.....

12. What challenges have you faced when using podcasts in your teaching? (Select all that apply)

- Lack of technical resources
- Difficulty in finding relevant content
- Limited class time
- Students' lack of interest

- Other (please specify):

.....

D. Support, Training, and Recommendations

13. Do you feel adequately trained to use podcasts as a teaching tool?

Yes

No

Somewhat

14. What support or resources would help you use podcasts more effectively in your teaching?

- Training workshops
- Access to curated podcast lists
- Technical support

- Other (please specify):

.....

15. Would you recommend using podcasts as a teaching tool for improving listening skills in EFL classes?

Yes

No

Not sure

16. What improvement or suggestions do you have for making podcasts more effective in EFL teaching? Feel free to include specific examples or ideas.

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Your responses are greatly appreciated! Thank you for your participation.